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Jean Monnet Network

Creating a European ‘Rearmament Bank’ –politically expedient but operationally tricky

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Worries about the disengagement of the second Trump administration from European security have created significant political momentum in the European Union and the United Kingdom to find alternative mechanisms to provide further funding for armaments. A number of European national governments — notably Germany¹ — have made strong commitments to increase military expenditure, while others — notably Poland² — have called for national promotional bank institutions to lend more to the defence industrial sector and fund military infrastructure. At the same time, several European countries are struggling under high debt loads and look to supranational mechanisms to shift the burden. One of the most likely options at this stage is the creation of a new multilateral financial mechanism charged with funding the defence buildup³ — an option likely to be soon endorsed in principle by EU member states. Various concrete proposals are circulating as to what

such a mechanism might look like, including a European Rearmament Bank (from the UK Treasury),⁴ a Defence, Security and Resilience Bank,⁵ or a European 'Weapons Stockpile' Fund (also from the UK Treasury).⁶ It is generally expected that the future defence financing mechanism would be able to mobilise around €200bn over a prolonged period and could thereby contribute significantly to meeting Europe's estimated defence investment needs of €500bn over the coming decade.⁷

The proponents of creating a new European financial institution draw explicitly on the precedent of the creation of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) following the fall of the Iron Curtain. But while the EBRD offers an attractive template with clear financial and political advantages, European policymakers should not ignore the wider governance issues that may

¹ Nöstlinger, N. (2025) 'German parliament passes historic spending reforms', *Politico*, 18 March; <https://www.politico.eu/article/germany-parliament-spending-reforms-defense-military-infrastructure-friedrich-merz/>

² Czekaj, M. & Postula, M. (2025) 'Development banks as key players in defense financing', *Politico*, 11 March;

<https://www.politico.eu/sponsored-content/development-banks-as-key-players-in-defense-financing/>

³ Wolff, G., Steinbach, A. & Zettermeyer, J. (2025) 'The governance and funding of European rearmament', Bruegel, Policy Brief, 7 April; <https://www.bruegel.org/policy-brief/governance-and-funding-european-rearmament>

⁴ Tamma, P., Foy, H., Parker, G. & Fleming, S. (2025) 'EU and UK in talks about Europe-wide defence funding amid fear of US pullback', *Financial Times*,

24 February; <https://www.ft.com/content/1a828a79-2bf1-4e3d-9136-83f110315645?>

⁵ Harding, R. (2025) 'Now is the moment for a multilateral defence bank', *Financial Times*, 9 April; <https://www.ft.com/content/afd25903-e96f-4270-a292-fd2a3671a524>

⁶ Tamma, P. (2025) 'UK floats plan for joint European fund to 'stockpile' weapons', *Financial Times*, 2 April; <https://www.ft.com/content/93d7168b-75a3-41e3-ba5a-4f378b93a709>

⁷ Von der Leyen, U. (2024) 'Opening remarks by President von der Leyen at the joint press conference with President Michel and Belgian President De Croo following the meeting of the European Council of 27 June 2024', Statement, European Commission, 28 June; https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/STATEMENT_24_3541

arise from adding another institution to the European public financial landscape.

A quick glance at the EBRD's history suffices to illustrate its appeal as a blueprint for a defence-themed institution. The EBRD was created in 1990 with the mandate to finance the transition of central and eastern European countries to market economies and to support democratic development.⁸ Within less than a year, the EBRD disbursed its first loans — a development of astonishing speed by the standards of multilateral institutions, and precisely to what proponents of a European defence financing mechanism aspire.

As with the EBRD, the mechanisms currently under discussion would remain under the control of national governments and outside the EU's institutional framework. In the EBRD's case, this approach ensured a larger participation — its initial shareholders were forty countries, including the United States and the Soviet Union, as well as the EU (represented by the European Commission) and the European Investment Bank (EIB). A similar intergovernmental structure for

a defence institution would allow neutral and Russia-friendly EU member states to opt out, while enabling non-EU NATO members, not least the UK and Norway, to participate. Furthermore, the UK Treasury's proposals could also allow for the European Commission and the EIB to become shareholders, as has been the case for the EBRD. Yet this prospect appears more remote, since EU external agreements in the realm of defence are subject to unanimity voting requirements and could easily be blocked.

The idea that a new defence financing mechanism would be set up as a temporary body — which can be found in several proposals — likewise draws on a precedent in the EBRD's statutes. The EBRD was subject to a sunset clause — it was to be wound up once the transition in central and eastern Europe had been accomplished. However, 35 years after its creation, and with its initial goals largely met, the Bank is still operating and expanding — in the number of its national shareholders, capital subscription, lending activities and lending countries. The inclusion of a sunset clause in current proposals is likely intended to make the creation of a new defence

⁸ Hodson, D., Howarth, D., Mugnai, I., & Spielberger, L. (forthcoming) *Banking on Europe: How the EU Became a Sovereign-Style Borrower and How It*

Should Be Held to Account, Oxford: Oxford University Press.

financing mechanism more politically palatable. However, it is hard to believe that a new defence financing mechanism would not become a permanent body if it operates successfully. The EBRD has shown that international public financial institutions can outlive their original purposes and thrive.

We can also consider the precedent of the complementarity of lending activities. In the 1990s, the EBRD focused upon lending in central and eastern Europe to higher-risk small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), while the EIB focused its lending activities upon large infrastructural projects. Lending activities in the military sector hold similar potential for synergies between institutions with different business models.

In early March, EU heads of government and state agreed to call upon the EIB's Board of Governors 'to urgently continue to adapt the EIB's practices for lending to the defence industry, notably by re-evaluating the list of excluded activities and by increasing the volume of available

funding in the field of security and defence'.⁹ Following suit, on 21 March, the EIB announced that it was shifting its lending activities to cover a range of military infrastructures, equipment, services and technologies — *excluding* weapons and armaments.¹⁰ The implication is that, to avoid unproductive overlaps, a new defence financing mechanism would ideally lend to borrowers and activities which the EIB was compelled by its mandate to spurn. A clear lending focus on SMEs and lethal equipment, notably ammunition, seems advisable to maintain an institutional balance between different European lenders in the realm of defence.

Yet even in that case, the EBRD's experience offers cautionary tales that proponents of new defence financing mechanisms in Europe should consider. Despite its rapid creation, and its novel business model, the EBRD struggled to overtake legacy institutions. Throughout the 1990s, the EIB lent far more to central and eastern Europe than did the EBRD. In the realm of defence, where procurement is particularly sensitive, it may thus prove particularly tricky to scale up lending. It

⁹ European Council (2025) 'European Council conclusions on European defence', 6 March, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2025/03/06/european-council-conclusions-on-european-defence/>

¹⁰ European Investment Bank (2025) 'EIB steps up financing for European security and defence and critical raw materials', 21 March; <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2025-156-eib-steps-up-financing-for-european-security-and-defence-and-critical-raw-materials>

is in this respect striking that a number of the proposals foresee new, joint procurement mechanisms alongside the new defence financing mechanism created — an idea recently endorsed by the new German government.¹¹ Nevertheless, allocating tens of billions of defence contracts per year through a novel procurement scheme seems like a tall order. No matter the political will behind a new defence financing mechanism, building a project pipeline and finalising projects takes time.

Other concerns remain. The creation of a new multilateral public bank, especially one outside the EU institutional framework, would likely increase fragmentation and coordination problems among European public lenders. A purely intergovernmental body would lack an institutional counterpart to coordinate its operations with a broader political agenda. Such coordination problems have long been apparent in EIB and EBRD lending,¹² and yet the proposal to

create a new European development bank by the Wieser group in 2019 still failed to gain political approval.¹³ Currently the lending activities of Europe's public financial institutions are coordinated under the aegis of the EU, through initiatives such as InvestEU, Team Europe and the EU's Global Gateway. However, neither the Commission's political guidance, nor the EU budget guarantees available under these frameworks would be available to a standalone institution focused specifically on lending for armament production. Achieving coordination with the EU's Defence Industrial Strategy might therefore prove challenging.

Moreover, on 19 March, the European Commission also proposed the Security Action for Europe (SAFE) proposal which was adopted by EU member states on 27 May. SAFE empowers the Commission to raise upwards of €150bn for expenditure on armaments.¹⁴ Both SAFE and the

¹¹ Pineau, E. (2025) 'EU needs joint approach to defence procurement, Germany's Pistorius says', Reuters, 13 March; <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/european-defence-ministers-meet-paris-discuss-ukraine-rearmament-2025-03-12/>

¹² Clifton, J. & Howarth, D. (2025) 'Realigning European public financial architecture for the twenty-first century', *Journal of Economic Policy Reform*, 28(1), pp. 1-11; <https://doi.org/10.1080/17487870.2024.2438396>;

Clifton, J., Díaz-Fuentes, D., Gómez Peña, A. L. & Howarth, D. (2025) 'Lending Overlap in Europe's Financial Architecture: A Comparative Analysis', *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research*

and Practice, 27(1), pp. 62-80; <https://doi.org/10.1080/13876988.2024.2380400>

¹³ Hodson, D. & Howarth, D. (2024) 'From the Wieser report to team Europe: explaining the 'battle of the banks' in development finance', *Journal of European Public Policy*, 31(9), 2611-2635; <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2023.2221301>

¹⁴ European Commission (2025) 'Commission unveils the White Paper for European Defence and the ReArm Europe Plan/Readiness 2030', Press Release, 19 March, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_793; Council of the EU (2025) 'SAFE: Council adopts €150 billion boost for joint procurement on European security and defence', Press release, 27 May,

Rearmament Bank proposed by the UK Treasury aim to provide loans to national governments to finance defence expenditures, yet neither their lending rates, nor the objectives that they fund would likely be subject to any coordination. Indeed, the creation of two defence financing mechanisms could lead to further competition between European lenders. These mechanisms could end up competing on lending terms, rather than exploiting synergies and economies of scale. EU member states agreed to allow candidate countries, potential candidates, acceding countries and countries that have signed a Security and Defence Partnership with the EU — including the UK — to join common procurements funded through SAFE. However, such joint procurement for projects creates yet another risk of unhelpful competition.

The creation of another public European lender also carries the risk of further undermining parliamentary control, which is especially critical in a domain as sensitive as defence. In a [recent article](#),¹⁵ we identified significant accountability gaps for existing pan-

European public borrowers, including both the EBRD and the EIB, which would likely be replicated with the creation of a new defence financing mechanism. The parliaments of shareholder states normally engage in little if any monitoring of their national directors, and it can be questioned whether NATO's Parliamentary Assembly could provide sufficient monitoring of a defence-themed lender. Likewise, bespoke audit arrangements would be needed to ensure financial oversight. For all the current urgency to expedite a European defence buildup, such important political questions should not be brushed aside.

New initiatives to invest in the defence capacities of European countries are sorely needed. Thus, we keenly welcome the recent proposals to create a new European defence financing mechanism. For advocates of a new European mechanism, the institutional template of the EBRD carries undeniable short-run advantages in terms of political feasibility. However, in the longer run, the creation of a Rearmament Bank, a

<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2025/05/27/safe-council-adopts-150-billion-boost-for-joint-procurement-on-european-security-and-defence/>.

¹⁵ Hodson, D., Howarth, D., Mugnai, I. & Spielberger, L. (2025) 'Accountability in pan-European borrowing: mind the gap', *West European Politics*, 48(3), 696–722;

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2024.2321559>;

see also: Hodson, D., Howarth, D., Mugnai, I., & Spielberger, L. (forthcoming) *Banking on Europe: How the EU Became a Sovereign-Style Borrower and How It Should Be Held to Account*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Weapons Stockpile Fund, or whatever name is assigned to the new defence financing mechanism, risks further undermining coherence and accountability in the European public financial landscape. This is not a reason to abandon the project. However, European leaders should ensure that they follow the norms of good governance and democratic accountability in their funding arrangements that they seek to defend within and beyond the EU.

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